

ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article talks about the foreign economic relations of our country, about the econometric analysis of the foreign economic activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *external, communication, economy, activity, investment, control, cooperation, business, security.*

The Republic of Uzbekistan conducts an open, mutually beneficial and constructive foreign policy based on its national interests. The modern political course of the republic is formed based on the rapidly changing situation in the world and in the region, as well as large-scale changes within the country. The main goal of the foreign political activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the independence and sovereignty of the state, its place in the international arena and to strengthen its role, to create an environment of security, stability and harmonious neighborhood around it, to actively promote the foreign economic interests of the republic.

Consistent measures are being taken in our country to liberalize foreign economic activity, increase export potential, increase investment attractiveness and improve customs administration. At the same time, phytosanitary, sanitary-epidemiological, veterinary, environmental to study the activities of control bodies and certification bodies (in the next place - authorized bodies) as a result, the need to increase the effectiveness and speed of their control functions in relation to goods and vehicles passing through the state border of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the need to improve interdepartmental electronic cooperation through rapid implementation indicating its existence. further improvement of administrative procedures in the implementation of foreign economic activities, improvement of business conditions, as well as the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 and the Republic of Uzbekistan Decision PQ-4059 of the President of December 12, 2018 "On measures for technical regulation, standardization, certification and further development of metrology systems" is a clear confirmation of this. in particular, if we consider this only as an example of the metallurgical industry, the external economic activity of JSC "Almaliq KMK", which is one of the leading enterprises of the metallurgical industry of Uzbekistan and the largest mining and metallurgical enterprise of the CIS countries, is a producer of quality products in the world market aimed at confirming as an enterprise and a reliable business partner. many programs are being developed for this purpose, and this can be achieved by increasing the quality of the product. At present, the combine produces more than 18 types of products, which are sold inside and outside the country. In this case, the export share is more than 70% of the total production volume.

In its foreign economic activity, the combine attracts foreign investments and conducts its active investment policy. The European bank "ABN AMRO" acted as an agent for the loan transaction. this loan was given directly to "Almaliq KMK" JSC by the syndicate of first-class international banks without the guarantees of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and this was an unusual event that happened in the history of independent Uzbekistan. Copper cathodes are traded on the London Metal Exchange for the record, in August 2005, the automatic packaging

line for copper cathodes was installed and put into operation at the plant. During 2005, the company implemented the Quality Management System according to the ISO 9001:2008 International Standard. Two large plants were launched: Angren copper pipe plant and Jizzakh cement plant. These facilities are part of investment projects for the production of new types of products. In particular, the unitary enterprise "Angren pipe factory" was established in the "Angren" free industrial zone, which has the annual production capacity of 8,000 tons of copper pipes of various diameters. The company plans to export 95% of its products.

econometrics (Greek: the art of managing a household and...metry), econometrics is a science that deals with the analysis of economic processes, the development and application of mathematical and economic statistical methods and models for processing economic information. Econometrics studies specific quantitative laws and relationships of economic events and processes using mathematical and statistical methods and models. Statistics with the help of models used in econometrics.

Quantitative results are obtained based on forecast and plan data. The emergence of econometrics is related to the need for economic statistical methods and guidelines for economic analysis and provision.

The mathematical study of economic-statistical data began at the end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century. In the 20s and 30s of the 20th century, econometrics emerged as an independent science. The term "econometrics" was originally coined by the Polish economist A. Chompa (1910), Norwegian economist, one of the founders of the International Econometric Society (1930). R. Frisch gave it a scientific direction (1926). Initially, within the framework of econometrics, analytical and statistical models representing correlational relations between economic processes and factors affecting them were developed. Economic growth models were used in the analysis of economic development. Russian scientist L.V. Kantorovich made a great contribution to the development of normative models.

Many forecasting problems can be solved with high accuracy using current econometric methods. In the present period, econometrics is used to improve the mathematical methods of economic development, justify the economic cycle, calculate demand and supply indicators, evaluate the variability of demand, analyze the changes in production costs and accumulation rates. It is used in the study of inter-industry relations of production and in the research and analysis of other issues.

In conclusion, it should be said that Uzbekistan's entry into the processes of international economic integration is increasing the internal and external potential of our republic. Thanks to Uzbekistan's participation in the integration structures, its bilateral and multilateral international relations are expanding, and it is recognized by the world community.

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